

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SITTING-ROCKER BOARD BALANCE TRAINING IN STROKE PATIENTS: A PILOT STUDY

Dr. Muslim Khan^{*1}, Prof Dr Sajid Rashid², Dr. Muhammad Adnan³, Dr. Nisaruddin⁴,
Dr Moatasim Shah⁵

^{*1}Associate Prof, IQRA National University, Swat, Pakistan

²Multan Medical and Dental College Principal

³Director Physiotherapy & Rehabilitation, City University Peshawar

⁴Associate Prof, 8Saidu Medical College, Saidu Sharif, Swat, Pakistan

⁵Clinical & lecturer Physical therapy, Habib Physical therapy Complex / Mehboob Medical Institute, Hayatabad, Peshawar

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Corresponding Author: *

Dr. Muslim Khan

Abstract

Background: Stroke is the leading cause of neurological deficits and disability worldwide. Stroke rehabilitation involves a holistic approach that incorporates various skills and specialties. Balance recovery is a vital part of stroke rehabilitation, and extensive work has shown that balance training based on functional skills, task-oriented activities, and training under different conditions to provide a variety of sensory inputs is effective for stroke patients. Compared to stable surfaces, unstable surfaces are more effective in helping stroke patients regain balance. Rocker board balance training has proven effective for patients with spinal cord injuries, but its effectiveness in stroke patients has not been thoroughly studied. The aim of this study is to determine the effectiveness of using a rocker board in sitting to improve balance in stroke patients.

Method: Ten stroke patients were selected for this pilot study using purposive sampling and were randomly assigned to two groups (control group n=5, treatment group n=5) at King Hospital, Swat. The control group (CG) received conventional physical therapy to improve balance, while the treatment group (TG) received conventional physical therapy plus rocker balance training. The Berg Balance Scale was used as the outcome measure, and the Wilcoxon signed-rank test and Mann-Whitney test were used to compare pre-test and post-test scores of both groups.

Results: The results of the study show that both groups improved significantly when comparing pre- and post-test results; however, greater improvement in balance was observed in the TG compared to the CG, with a Pvalue > 0.05.

Conclusion: The results of this study show that rocker board training is effective in improving balance in stroke patients.

INTRODUCTION

Stroke is the 3rd cause of death globally; from 1990-2007 age standardized year of life lost (YLL) increased by 12.9% (10.6-15.2) & from 2007-2017 by 12.1% , while the stroke incidence

increased 5.29Million (5.22-5.40) to 6.17 Million (6.4-6.33) from 2007-2017-3 ,thus, it increased DALYs (disability adjusted life years) due to multifaceted morbidity & effects of longevity fom

3.54 to 9.66% in the period 1990-2013 as reported GBD statistic(Global burden of the Diseases)⁴. High income countries (HIC) recorded a 42% decrease in the stroke while on the other hand low- & middle-income countries (LMIC) showed 100% increase in the last 3-4 decades⁵. The statistics records that there are around 62 million stroke survivors globally while 1/3rd among them are living with severe disabilities⁴. It has been estimated that more than 80%

DALYs occurs in LMIC^{6,7}. In spite of the recent effective advancement made in the management of the stroke such as; thrombolytic & endovascular interventions stroke remains one of the most common cause of disability worldwide⁸. Post-stroke disability is still a major health burden^{9,10}. There is variation in the rehabilitation programs provided to the stroke patients worldwide & the quality & content of the program depends mostly on the medical & financial resources¹⁰.

Stroke is the most prevalent cause of neurological deficits & disability worldwide. Stroke rehabilitation is a holistic approach-based intervention involving different skills & specialties. Balance recovery is a crucial component of stroke recovery; however, most work carried out on stroke balance focuses on functional skills, task-oriented activities & training under varied conditions, providing a range of sensory inputs that are effective in stroke patients. Compared to a stable surface, an unstable surface is found to be more effective in helping stroke patients regain balance. Rocker board balance training is practical for balance training in patients with spinal cord injuries. Still, in stroke patients, the effectiveness of rocker board balance training has not been studied effectively. This study aims to determine the effectiveness of the rocker board in improving balance for sitting stroke patients.

The primary deficits of imbalance in stroke population are the inability of the patient to centrally integrate inputs (visual, somatosensory, vestibular), leading to recurrent falls & difficulty in performing ADLs^{14,15}. The somatosensory system provides motion information & the

position sense to the CNS, referencing the supporting surface & constant changes in the foot's surface dynamics. 15 Stroke patients are deficient in somatosensory input generation & its central coordination. Thus, exercise interventions that utilize vision & surface manipulation are an effective means for challenging stroke patients to improve their balance.

It has been reported that the rocker board (wobble boards) improves both static & dynamic balance in stroke patients. The study duration was only 6 weeks, which can be interpreted as a rocker board for balance improvement in the stroke population, being highly cost-effective & instant intervention compared to other conventional physical therapy approaches for balance improvement^{17,18}. It has also been reported in another study that, compared to stable surface balance training, unstable surface training is more effective for improving balance in stroke patients. 20 Another study carried out on spinal cord injury patients reported that 4 weeks of balance training on a rocker board improved patients' sitting balance on the modified functional reach test as an outcome measure^{11,12}.

Stroke balance has been studied before, with an intense focus on task-oriented activities & training surfaces that alter somatosensory inputs & has been reported to be effective for improving balance in stroke patients. Unstable surface is effective for the balance as compared to stable surfaces, which may be caused by the constant changes in the somatosensory inputs during the balance training; however, rocker board balance training in stroke patients has not been studied extensively in standing, as, on the other hand, rocker board training in sitting has been found effective in the SCI population^{6,7}. The impact produced by the rocker board in SCI patients may be replicated in stroke patients as well; therefore, this study aims to find out the effectiveness of the rocker board in sitting for balance improvement in stroke patients.

Methodology:

Ten stroke patients were selected for this pilot study based on purposive sampling & randomly

assigned into two groups (control group, n = 5, Treatment group, n = 5) at King Hospital, Swat. The control group (CG) received conventional physical therapy for balance improvement, while the treatment group (TG) received traditional physical therapy & rocker balance training. The balance exercise used for TG was a modified form of exercise previously used by Kim JH21. According to the Kim JH protocol study, the subject sat on a square place on a stable floor with straight legs to measure the reach distance of each patient enrolled in the study. The distances calculated are a) forward reach distance to the affected side, and b) forward reach distance to the unaffected side. C) Patient reaching forward (forward distance). A specified bar was placed each time 2 centimetres beyond the previous measure or initial maximum. The rocker board was then placed on the stable surface of the floor in the physical therapy department. Each patient must sit at the centre of the board, keeping their legs straight & forward & at the same time ensuring that the rocker board doesn't tilt. Each study subject sits on the board and performs a forward reach, a side reach to the affected side & side reach to the unaffected side, while trying to reach the bar. The bar touched was a successful attempt only & recorded. For the forward reach, each patient has to ask to extend both hands forward. Each task was performed 4 times by each study subject, comprising 16 repetitions with a 40-60s break in between the two consecutive attempts. The frequency of interventions was as follows: 16 repetitions /session/day, 5days/week for two successive weeks, 21,25. The conventional physical therapy intervention for the CG & TG was as follows: stretching &

strengthening exercises of the lower & upper limbs. The frequency of conventional exercise was 1-3 sets of 10-15 repetitions /sessions, 5days/week for two consecutive weeks. All study subjects were assessed initially with BBS (pre-test score) & re-assessed after the completion of the 2 weeks (post-test score). Before the study was conducted, administrative approval was obtained from the concerned hospital. The study's subjects were then briefed & written consent was obtained. The inclusion criteria for the study were a) chronic stroke patients irrespective of their gender, aged 35-60years with the motor assessment scale in sitting score 3 b) the selected study's participants must not have any visual or sensory inputs, while the exclusion criteria were a) chronic patients with cognitive deficits or having other neurological disorders as comorbid conditions such as; multiple sclerosis, Parkinson's disease, osteoarthritis, ligaments injuries etc. b) stroke patients not willing to participate in the study or have balance training other than the study's balance training simultaneously. Berg balance scale, rocker board & parallel bar were used as outcome measures & Wilcoxon signed-rank test was used to compare the improvement between groups & Mann-Whitney test was used to compare the pre-test & post-test scores of both groups. For the data analysis, SPSS V.23 was used.

Results:

The result of the study shows that both groups improved significantly by comparing pre-& post-test of the study; however, greater improvement in balance was observed in the TG as compared to the CG, with a P-value >0.04.

Table 1: Baseline study variables

Group	Age (Means± SD)	Time since the stroke onset, Age (Means± SD)
TG	49.3 ± 2.3	4.5±1.2
CG	51.4±3.5	4.5±1.4

In the TG BBS score improved from 23.42± 1.2 to 29±2.3 while in the CG, it was improved from 24.01±1.1 to 27.34±3.4 at the P-value >.005. (Table-2)

Table 2: BBS score within the group by comparing pre- & post-test scores

Group	Pre-test score	Post-test score	P-values
TG	23.42± 1.2	29±2.3	>0.05
CG	24.01±1.1	27.34±3.4	>0.05

Table 3: Difference between the two groups

TG	CG	P-values
29±2.3	27.34±3.4	>0.05

Discussion: Stroke is the most prevalent cause of neurological deficits & disability worldwide. Stroke rehabilitation is a holistic approach-based intervention involving different skills & specialties. Balance recovery is a crucial component of stroke recovery. However, the majority of work on stroke balance has focused on functional skills, task-oriented activities & training under varied conditions, providing a range of sensory inputs, which are effective in stroke patients. Compared to a stable surface, an unstable surface is found to be more effective in helping stroke patients regain balance. Rocker board balance training is practical for balance training in patients with spinal cord injuries. Still, in stroke patients, the effectiveness of rocker board balance training has not been studied effectively. This study aims to determine the effectiveness of the rocker board in improving balance for sitting stroke patients. The results of the study show that both groups improved significantly when comparing the pre- and post-tests; however, greater improvement in balance was observed in the TG compared to the CG, with a P-value greater than 0.05. The result of this study is in line with the other research carried out in India²⁵. The improvement in the BBS score may be explained by the development of compensatory posture strategy & neural plasticity regained during the extensive balance training on the rocker board^{14,15}. Another theory that has been postulated suggests that the improvement is possibly due to an increase in neurotransfer through the descending corticospinal tracts, which innervate the muscles of the trunk. 15

Shummway Cook suggests that excessive external swing on the rocker board leads to the generation of postural orientation by alteration of the somatosensory system of the body, leading further to improved postural strategy & control²³. Another theory proposed by Granacher et al. suggests that the unstable surface of the rocker board sensitizes the muscle spindle through the activation of gamma motor neurons, resulting in the modulation of motor output in the form of improved postural control.

Limitations: 1) small sample size & purposive sampling, 2) the patients need to be followed up for a more extended period of time.

Conclusion: The result of this study suggests that rocker board training is practical for the improvement of balance in stroke patients.

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